

The Cost-Effective Analysis of Energy Storage Systems of Information and Communication Technology Schools with Different Pricing Schemes

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ABSTRACT: The paper presents research on the cost-effective analysis of different energy storage systems of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) schools in Punjab Pakistan. As we know that the world is moving towards renewable energy-based production of electricity, which involves the modernization of electricity networks in the form of smart grids allowing the end-users to participate actively in cost management as well as generation of electricity at their own level through PV systems, wind mills with the aid of storage systems. Literature review includes the different storage schemes along with their pricing strategies. Secondly the comparison of using parameters and optimization algorithms is also carried out. The purpose of comparison is to find out which type of system is more efficient regarding the cost, sustainability and resiliency for multicultural ICT educational school systems. The contribution to this research includes the cost optimizing comparison of lithium-ion battery and lead-acid battery for similar system. The schematic diagram is shown in paper. The methodology includes load profile, electricity tariff data for the location. Simulation is done on the software HOMER-pro, calculating the cost tracking. The discussion and conclusion include the results of simulations which provides us information about which system is more suitable regarding the cost efficacy for ICT schools. The results are made through algorithms and graphical representation that shows the outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Schools, Levelled cost of energy (LCOE), battery energy storage systems (ESS), Fuel cells, lead-acid batteries

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1. Introduction

Renewable power sources such as solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind have proven to be challenging to integrate and adapt due to their instability or the ways in which individuals consume energy. When integrating a Battery Storage Energy System (BESS) using standard and renewable power sources, it is necessary to examine their current status from an operating standpoint. These consist of figuring out how much power is available and how long it will take to discharge it, estimating the amount of storage and how long it will take, and computing delivery and distribution capacity. A BESS at the house level might improve power system performance since time-of-use (TOU) and real-time (RT) dynamic pricing systems are being deployed as traditional distribution systems theoretically evolve toward the Smart Grid (SG), and RT programs. A major factor in the effective adoption as well as integration of these innovations is the efficient functioning of ESSs while accounting for an RT pricing tariff.

Among other battery technologies, lead-acid, sodium-sulfur, and the lithium-ion or Li-ion, batteries can be used to create energy storage systems (ESS); however, these systems lack some of the characteristics of efficient ESS systems [1,2]. The constraints include inadequate concentrations of power and energy, a shorter lifespan in comparison [3] to other energy storage systems, and, to a lesser extent, a high initial cost per unit of store capacity, particularly for the lithium-ion and sodium-sulfur cells [9, 10].

Currently providing over twenty-five percent of the electricity consumed in three countries globally, wind energy is expected to continue to grow in share of the energy system as onshore wind technology develops [1]. The position provided by offshore wind minimizes space constraints and is next to popular seaside locations. In addition to being quicker and more consistent than winds on land, offshore projects experience higher wind speeds [2].

The potential to use time-shifting to take advantage of energy arbitrage is one advantage of using wind energy for storage. Battery costs are too high for most energy exchange markets to break even, according to modeling and earlier research [15,18]. Salles [17] replicated the energy storage facilities in the PJM, a mid-Atlantic electricity transmission company, from 2008 for 2014 with batteries construction costs of \$200/kilowatt and discovered that, under ideal conditions, this revenue was sufficient to break even; over the following decades, nevertheless, other locations required installation costs of half the price to achieve break-even? Scheduling energy production, balancing the infrastructure, and supplying extra peak reserves are thus the most practical potential benefits of wind power storing [3,9].

The interconnection between culture and language has gained substantial recognition, leading to a significant shift in second and foreign language teaching towards fostering intercultural competence (IC). This transition has been bolstered by advancements in communication technologies, notably telecollaboration, which has shown promise in enhancing both linguistic and intercultural skills, particularly when facilitated by proficient teachers. Despite this, IC teaching in Pakistani multicultural school remains predominantly focused on imparting cultural knowledge, with limited implementation of telecollaboration projects and an insufficient evaluation of teachers' telecollaborative capabilities. The main challenge these days for ICT schools in Punjab Pakistan in the total cost of ownership (TCO) for energy storage systems and this paper present solution to that problem.

The work employs a swarm-based meta-heuristic search technique for Home Load Energy Management setups (HLEMs) to schedule smart appliances with the lowest energy costs by utilizing the bidirectional energy flow of EVs for ICT educational school systems. In

order to achieve the proper scheduling of home loads, the Instant state of charge (IOC) level of an electric vehicle (EV) is employed to consider the energy threshold with a cost-effective user opulence. The problem's objective is to minimize the peak to average ratio of a typical smart house and arrange the home loads and EV to incur the lowest possible daily energy expenditure bill while maximizing the utilization of daily average power. A meta-heuristic population-based elephant herding optimization method is used to achieve this.

2. Literature Review

For powering a house BESS and solar panels mounted on an energy system. In this technique, estimations of PV generation as well as loading demand are employed. Through application of individual linear approximation of the goal function included inside a linear-programming (LP) problem, the control method seeks to minimize the overall power cost by resolving the relevant optimal storage control issue.

In reaction to the energy regulation that restricts residential customers' ability to purchase power from the SG, a BESS mechanism for control based on the use of dynamic programming (DP) was created in [12]. A backward tracking mechanism is added to prevent solutions that might negatively impact a battery energy storage system's sustainability. The approach being supplied takes certain discrete states into account for charging and discharging scenarios. In order to lessen the impact of forecasting errors on energy prices, load demand, and particularly renewable generation, corrective management techniques are employed during real-time operation.

Power-to-heat transfer was the focal point of an optimization method that was presented in [18] to optimize ESS performance. With regard for the energy stored & the maximum amount of charging power permitted at each time step, electricity-storage systems (ESSs) are mainly intended to be charged for low prices. First, a mathematical formula that does not take energy losses into consideration is constructed. The next action is to build two optimization models that treat loss of energy as a variable and a constant.

In [20], a control method was developed based on the pseudo-SOC principle to include additional services offered by distributed generators. The algorithm uses data from the energy system's operation, such as a SOC and the quantity of PV generation, to calculate the best operating strategy for the BESS and to predict the voltage operating conditions in real time. The integration of an oversight method focused on reducing total costs in [21] has tackled peak-load shaved, energy-curve smoothing out, voltages management, renewable power manufacturing, and additional strategy and operational difficulties. This approach bases peak-load shaving costs on the amount of energy passing through the allocation transformer. Using this approach, the relevant optimization issue is solved by using an ordered quadratic programming technique.

Currently, they are governed by several nations, including South Korea, Australia, Germany, Ireland, Cape Verde, Japan, and Kenya. Numerous current methods for the best management of laboratory animals (LABs) functioning under dynamic pricing offer logical solutions when seen through the lens of mathematics. Nevertheless, a lot of these approaches can't explain the nonlinear behavior of the LAB, such the bidirectional converter's fluctuating efficiency, the accusation controller's regulation of voltage, and the gassing phenomenon of electrochemical processes. The charge control unit of a standard LAB decreases the appropriate current during the process of charging to counteract the consequences of the gassing phenomena. This maintains the 2.23 V/cell battery voltage constant. As so, a nonlinear and progressive reduction in the quantity of electricity acquired from the grid occurs. However, there is nonlinear behavior in the power converter's

efficiency. In particular, the converter's conversion efficiency increases with transmitted power but is comparatively poor when it transmits less power in relation to the device's rated capacity. The system's economic performance may be impacted by this fact, which may also have an impact on the power transfer within the LAB and the SG.

In order to demonstrate the noteworthy advantages of combining renewable energy generation and shared energy storage (ESS), HENBO energy storing has already set up a shared in Upper lands, Northern Irish. Moreover, Tesla plans to build the biggest shared energy system across the globe in South Australia to increase the stability and reliability of the regional electrical grid. We utilize the installation and management of a bulk ESS by an ESP in a way that guarantees that all users profit equally through the ESS as our example. When compared to the scenario of individual ESSs, It showed that the adoption of a shared ESS can increase end users' profitability up as much as 10%.

Demand side control (DSM) is a strategy that, among other things, use intelligent energy pricing strategies to incentivize energy users to adhere to a consumption pattern that provides a beneficial trade-off between their desired pattern and the person that is cost-effective for the energy system. Lately, models for real-time pricing (RTP) have been created [25,26]. By directly linking the expenses of energy production, transmission, and distribution versus the retail price, their primary objective is to reduce the peak-to-average ratio of a particular customer group. RTP implementation begins with the establishment of a means of communication that is two between the end users and the ESP. Hence, a limited number of conversations are used to instantly settle the conflict between improving user happiness and lowering power costs [25,26].

Global energy storage needs will rise from 176.5 Gbps in 2017 to 266 GW by 2030, according to estimates from the European Energy Agency (IEA) [15]. Pumped hydroelectric electricity accounted for more than 96% of the energy storage system's installed grid capacity, which as of 2018 totaled 175.8 GW [16]. The system was expanding substantially. By 2040, the global energy storage industry will have grown to a total of 1095 GW, a significant growth rate considering current trends, predicts Bloomberg New Energy Finance.

Bloomberg New Energies Finance projects that during another 20 years, stationary storage of energy will rise 122 times, needing expenditures totaling in excess of \$662 billion [15, 16]. Oversupply of power into the grid occurs in several U.S. states during specific times of peak solar or wind output. It is possible that these regions will have to sell this energy for very little money on the wholesale market. In addition to effectively lowering wholesale volatility in prices and increasing overall grid efficiency, dynamic energy prices is a tried-and-true strategy that can help avert these particular situations [4]. Dynamic pricing has been included by several wholesalers and utility companies that sell power to smaller consumers via smart meters.

A number of pricing systems, including the time-of-use price system, which offers two or three price tags (such as "off-season," "mid-peak," and "peak times"), can be provided by dynamic pricing [16]. Second, dynamic pricing is viewed in immediate pricing, where the average consumer power price fluctuates hourly based on the energy wholesale market price in addition to an additional fee for transmission costs and a profit margin [17].

The primary function of stationary batteries linked to power systems is to store energy for later use, which is another use for batteries [22]. Reversible fuel cells, which operate in the unstable power markets, are among the potential storage technologies that seem to have received less attention in this research than they deserve. Before the fuel cells technologies—which are developing energy sources—can completely reach the market, a number of challenges must be resolved, including high initial system prices and

low system efficiency. As it happens, some of these problems can be resolved by legal frameworks and technical improvements working together.

The battery storage devices that are placed next to the turbines are quite small when compared to the power that they produce. GE constructed northwest Ireland's Tullahennel enterprise is a wind farm with 13 turbines that generates 37 MW of rated power. Each turbine has a Li-ion battery linked to it in order to offer 897 kWh of store [22]. A recent proposal to synchronize energy supply with peak consumption calls for the construction of a 10 w/40 MWh Ev battery and 144 MW wind farms by the Commonwealth of the state of Rhode Island [23]. Deepwater Wind is mulling about this concept. The Hornsdale Energy Reserve, which was built in South Australia in 2017, is the largest battery storage facility in the world. It combines 315 MW of wind energy with a score of 100 MW/129-kilowatt battery that is mostly used for grid stability [24].

It is crucial to confirm that the capacity is favorable and cost-effective when employing wind power for long-duration energy storage. The cost of power storage is generally heavily influenced by packaging, material, and research expenses. As of right now, Li-ion batteries are the most advanced and widely used technology available for electrical power storage. It is anticipated that between 2010 and 2018, Li-ion battery pack prices would decrease by 85%. [28]

3. Methodology

In order to lower power costs of ICT schools and thus managing TCO, the charging and discharge adjustments of BESS are the primary source of profit in this study's analysis of the economic advantages of BESS energy arbitrage. As a test case, research employs an industrial client. The program HOMER Grid is used. The proposed methods and topics of discussion are as follows:

Calculation Of Electricity Charge:

Applied tariff of LESCO is given as

Figure 1: Applied tariff of LESCO

SCHEDULE OF ELECTRICITY TARIFF W.E.F 12-02-2021

A1 General Supply Tariff-Residential						
Sr. No.	Tariff Category/Particulars	Fixed Charges Rs/KW/M	Uniform Tariff Variable Charges (Rs/kWh)		Applicable Variable Charges	
a)	For Sanctioned load less than 5 kW					
i	Up to 50 Units	–	4		3.95	
	For Consumption exceeding 50 Units				–	
ii	For first 100 Units	–	14.89		7.74	
iii	a.101-200 Units		16.41		10.06	
iii	b.201-300 Units	–	17.53		12.15	
iv	301-700 Units	–	19.07		19.55	
v	Above 700 Units	–	20.61		22.65	
b)	For Sanctioned load 5 kW & above					
			Peak	Off-Peak	Peak	Off-Peak
	Time of Use	–	20.27	13.1	22.65	16.33

Figure 2: Daily Profile**Figure 3: Seasonal Profile**

Electricity costs are considered a baseline for benefit comparisons, based on the load characteristics of industrial customers without energy storage system installation. For various contract capacities, simulations of the load, TOU rates, satisfying the electricity demand, BESS capacity allocation, electrical, and economic outcomes conducted. The above-mentioned results yielded the BESS capacity with the maximum project benefit. The study assesses the sensitivity of the price of electricity, the cost of major components, and the real interest rate based on the economical contract capacity and BESS capacity. Lastly, the outcomes can be utilized to assess the degree of influence on financial gains.

Economic Assignment Criteria:

Subsections 1 through 8 [28] provide the descriptions and calculations for the economic evaluation indicators used in this study.

Annual Rate of Real Interest

The difference between one-time and annualized costs is expressed in terms of the annual real interest rate (i).

In HOMER Grid software, the total NPC value denotes the system life cycle cost. The cash flow of the t -year over the factor and the initial capital cost is totaled, as shown in equation (2). Capital costs, operating costs, replacement costs, maintenance costs, etc. are included in the costs. Revenue is made up of selling electricity and the value salvaged at the end of its useful life.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{NPC is equal to } & -CF_0 + \{CF_1(1+i)^{-1} + CF_2(1+i)^{-2} \\
 & + CF_3(1+i)^{-3} + \dots + CF_n(1+i)^{-n}\} \\
 N = & -CF_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n CF_t(1+i)^{-t}
 \end{aligned}$$

t (2), where CF_t is the cash flow for the t-year. (According to the HOMER Grid software's definition, there are positive revenue and negative expenses.) (\$); i is the real interest rate for the year (%); N is the project lifetime (year); t is the number of years (year); CF_0 is the initial capital cost (\$).

The factor for capital recovery

The formula used to determine the present value of the annuity throughout the course of the project is called the capital recovery factor (CRF). Where t is the number of years (year) and i is the yearly real interest rate (%),

$$CRF(it) = i(1+i)^t / ((1+i)^t - 1)$$

Leveled Energy Cost:

The average cost of electricity per kWh of load use is the definition of leveled cost of energy, or LCOE, in this study. It is calculated by taking the total annualized load consumption and dividing it by the total annualized cost (TAC). \$/kWh is the unit of the LCOE. The annualized value of VOLUME 8, 2020 203737 C is known as the TAC.-T. Tsai et al.: Battery Energy Storage System for Behind-the-Meter Application NPC, Techno-Economic and Sizing Analysis, with \$/year as the unit of measurement. The following is the equation:

$$|NP \cdot C| \times CRF(iN) = TAC \quad (4)$$

$$LCOE = TACE' \quad (5)$$

where N is the project lifetime in years, and E_{prim} is the total annualized load consumption (kWh/year).

Figure 4: Load Profile

Project Benefit

The project benefit, expressed in dollars, is the difference between the present case's NPC and the reference case's NPC. A positive result shows that the present system saves money over the project lifetime compared to the base case system. The sign of the project benefit describes whether the current case compares favorably as an investment alternative with the reference case. The following is the equation:

$$PB = \{-CF_{c,0} + x_{nt} = kF_c t(1+i)^t\}$$

Return on Investment

The annual cost reductions in relation to the initial investment is known as the return on investment, or ROI. The return on investment is calculated by the software.

Discounted Payback Period

The amount of time it takes for the total discounted net cash flow to equal the initial investment in the project or asset is called the discounted payback period, or DPP. The year is its unit. The formula can be found in (8). DPP is equal to $t_{full} + C_{cap,last} / CF_{c,t_{full}+1} (1+i)^{t_{full}+1} - C_{ref,t_{full}+1} (1+i)^{t_{full}+1}$ (8), where t_{full} is the amount of time before the total cash flow turns positive (year). The capital cost that remains unrecovered after the total cash flow turns positive (\$) is known as $C_{cap,last}$.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Using Lead-Acid Battery

The schematic diagram is shown in the figure[5] below, using a wind turbine with BESS of lead-acid battery.

Figure 5: Schematic Diagram

Economic metrics are

- IRR = 95%
- ROI=76%
- Payback Period =1.17 yr

In case of lead-acid battery its energy in is 1731 Kwh/yr and energy out is approximately 1383KWh/yr, storage depletion of 1.40 KWh/yr, expected life of 2.58 years with losses 346 KWh/yr and average energy cost of 0.264 \$/KWh.

Figure 6: Optimization Graph Of Total Operating Cost

Cost Summary

The cost summary by using lead acid battery is given in the table below:
 Converter of 0.583kW
 Generator of 2.70kW

Table 1: Cost Summary (1)

	BASE CASE	LOWEST COST SYSTEM
NPC	\$56662	\$40898
Initial Capital	\$1350	\$3025
O&M	\$4270/yr	\$2930/yr
LCOE	\$1.07/kWh	\$0.769/kWh

Figure 7: Cash Flow Chart

The output of this is given in figure 8.

Figure 8: Output

Using Lithium-Ion Battery

Figure 9a: schematic diagram

The schematic diagram is shown in the figure[9a], using a wind turbine with BESS of lithium-ion battery.

With same load profile and location, replace lead-acid battery with lithium-ion battery.

Economic metrics are

- IRR = 94%
 - ROI=84%
- PAYBACK PERIOD =1.1 yr

In case of lithium-ion battery its energy in is 3318 Kwh/yr and energy out is approximately 2987 KWh/yr, storage depletion of 1.62 KWh/yr, expected life of 2.86 years with losses 332 KWh/yr and average energy cost of 0.254 \$/KWh.

Figure 10b: Optimization Graph

Cost Summary

The cost summary by using lead acid battery is given in the table below:

Converter of 2.20kW

Generator of 2.70kW

Table 2: Cost Summary

	Base Case	Lowest Cost System
NPC	\$56662	\$32461
Initial Capital	\$1350	\$3661
O&M	\$4270/yr	\$2228/yr
LCOE	\$1.07/kWh	\$0.611/kWh

Figure 11: Cash Flow Chart

The output is given in figure 12.

Figure 12: Output

Comparison Discussion

By comparing the properties of both the batteries it is proved that lithium-ion batteries are more preferable as its life is more, average energy cost is less. If we compare with different pricing factors like interest real rate (IRR) it is same but in case of return on investment (ROI) it is approximately 10% less than ROI at lead-acid BESS. Payback period of lithium-ion batteries is also less. LCOE and NPC are very less for lithium-ion batteries as shown in the Tables given above.

5. Recommendations

The industry is dominated by lithium-ion batteries, but under certain conditions, alternatives like compressed air storage and pumped hydro storage can provide a competitive edge, according to a cost-effective review of energy storage systems for ICT educational school systems. The pricing models that each system employs, such as capacity-based pricing and time-of-use prices, are critical in assessing their economic feasibility and TCO. This emphasizes the need of a customized strategy to optimize both affordability and efficiency so that to reap maximum benefit of the research for educational institutions.

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